

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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THE ROLE OF IMMUNOTHERAPY IN METASTATIC BREAST CANCER (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Resume. Breast cancer is a serious health problem worldwide. More than 1 million 200 thousand new cases of breast cancer are diagnosed annually, which is 10% of all oncological diseases in the world. Breast cancer is a disease in which pathological cells in the tissues of the mammary gland begin to divide uncontrollably and form a tumor. Without treatment, the tumor can spread to other areas of the body and lead to death. The article reflects new technologies for the diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer. New technologies for cancer staging, lymphatic dissection formed the basis of a new method for treating breast cancer. Thanks to the emergence of new technical means, the possibilities for more precise diagnostics of breast cancer and individualization of treatment with priority given to organ-preserving surgical interventions are increasing.

Keywords: breast cancer, lymph node, Immunotherapy, T cell, PD-L1 and PD-1

МЕТАСТАТИК КЎКРАК САРАТОНИДА ИММУНОТЕРАПИЯНИНГ РОЛИ (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРҲИ)

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Резюме. Кўкрак саратони бутун дунё бўйлаб жиддий соғлиқ муаммосидир. Ҳар йили кўкрак беши саратонининг 1 миллион 200 мингдан ортиқ янги ҳолатлари аниқланади, бу дунёдаги барча онкологик касалликларнинг 10 фоизини ташкил қилади. Кўкрак беши саратони - бу кўкрак тўқималаридаги гайритабиий ҳужайралар назоратсиз равишида бўлиниши бошлайдиган ва шунинг ҳосил қиладиган касаллик. Агар даволанмаса, ўсимта тананинг бошқа жойларига тарқалиши ва ўлимга олиб келиши мумкин. Мақолада кўкрак беши саратонини таъхислаш ва даволашнинг янги технологиялари акс эттирилган. Саратонни босқичма-босқич аниқлаш ва лимфа йўлини ажратишнинг янги технологиялари кўкрак беши саратонини даволашнинг янги усули учун асос бўлди. Янги техник воситаларнинг пайдо бўлиши туфайли кўкрак беши саратонини аниқроқ диагностика қилиш ва органларни сақловчи жарроҳлик амалиётига устувор аҳамият бериш билан даволашни индивидуаллаштириш имкониятлари ортиб бормоқда.

Калит сўзлар: кўкрак саратони, лимфа тугунлари, иммунотерапия, Т ҳужайра, PD-L1 ва PD-1

РОЛЬ ИММУНОТЕРАПИИ ПРИ МЕТАСТАТИЧЕСКОМ РАКЕ МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

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Резюме. Рак молочной железы-серьезная проблема здравоохранения во всем мире. Ежегодно выявляется более 1 млн 200 тыс. новых случаев РМЖ, что составляет 10 % всех онкологических заболеваний в мире. Рак молочной железы — заболевание, при котором патологические клетки в тканях молочной железы начинают бесконтрольно делиться и образуют опухоль. В отсутствие лечения опухоль может распространиться в другие области организма и привести к смерти. В статье отражены новые технологии диагностики и лечения рака молочной железы. Новые технологии стадирования рака, лимфатической диссекции легли в основу нового метода лечения рака молочной железы. Благодаря появлению новых технических средств повышаются возможности уточняющей диагностики рака молочной железы, индивидуализации лечения с приоритетом органосохраняющих хирургических вмешательств.

Ключевые слова: рак молочной железы, лимфатический узел, Иммунотерапия, Т-клетка, PD-L1 и PD-1

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Breast cancer tumor cells begin to grow in the milk ducts and/or lobules of glandular tissue. The earliest form (in situ) is not life-threatening and can be detected at an early stage. Tumor cells can spread to adjacent breast tissue (invasion). As the tumor continues to grow, a bulky formation or thickening occurs.

Despite significant advances in breast cancer treatment, new treatment approaches and strategies are needed to further improve disease outcomes and expand therapeutic options. Modern breast cancer treatment includes surgical, radiation, chemotherapeutic, hormonal, and targeted approaches. Despite their evolution, these methods face limitations, including resistance, side effects, and mixed efficacy in different patient groups. In this regard, the search for new therapeutic opportunities is an urgent task. It is noteworthy that although breast cancer is not traditionally considered highly immunogenic, studies show the presence in its microenvironment of a variety of immune cells, both innate and adaptive types. The use of immunotherapeutic agents aimed at enhancing the antitumor immune response is a promising direction in the treatment of breast cancer, which opens up new prospects in the fight against this disease. The role of the immune system in the prognosis and immunotherapy for breast cancer has long been underestimated. The attention of researchers and doctors was focused on the clinically significant biological features of tumor cells (the presence of estrogen and progesterone receptors, the proliferative index of tumor cells, overexpression of the HER2/neu protein), which determine the prognosis of the disease and the choice of individual treatment tactics.

Immunotherapy has already become an important component of the standard treatment of patients with advanced cancer. Most treatments include monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) that block immune checkpoints, in particular programmed cell death receptor 1 (PD-1) and its ligand 1 (PD-L1), or target T-lymphocyte-associated protein 4 (CTLA-4). Unlike other solid tumors (including colon and rectal cancer, ovarian cancer, melanoma) Breast cancer (BC) has not been classified as a highly immunogenic tumor for a long time. It was only after the discovery of the pathogenetic diversity of breast cancer that it became clear that at least two biological subtypes with high proliferative activity, triple negative and HER2-positive, possess certain features of immunogenicity. Immunotherapy is one of the most promising areas in the treatment of breast cancer (BC), especially in relation to the triple negative subtype. It is based on the fundamental principle of activation of the endogenous antitumor immune response. The main directions of immunotherapy • Immune response checkpoint inhibitors • Therapy using CAR-T cells • Vaccine therapy and the use of oncolytic viruses. Breast cancer was traditionally thought to be poorly immunogenic and yield a relatively lower mutation burden compared to 'inflamed' tumors, including melanoma and non-small cell lung carcinoma. Accumulated results have demonstrated that higher T lymphocyte infiltration was observed in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) breast cancer compared to estrogen receptor-positive, HER2-negative luminal breast cancer. Among molecular subtypes, single agent cancer immunotherapy showed the most promising results in TNBC. The development of immuno-oncology combinations is required to increase the clinical benefit of immunotherapy against breast cancer.

Breast cancer, in principle, has the ability to stimulate an immune response. It has been unequivocally established that some tumors undergo significant lymphocytic infiltration, and the more T cells are detected, the better the prognosis [2]. Over the past decade, studies of tumor pathology have demonstrated the role of the adaptive immune response in modulating tumor growth. A large number of type I lymphocytes infiltrating the tumor (TILs) correlates with a favorable prognosis for tumor diseases, including colon, ovarian, lung, and breast cancers [3, 4, 5-6]. The absolute number of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) is important in providing the body's potential immune defense against the tumor [7]. The magnitude of the adaptive immune response proved to be important for the prognosis of breast cancer.

Population studies of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TIL) have shown that the disease is immunogenic, and with breast cancer and HER2+ breast cancer, the greatest effect of an endogenous immune response is observed. The first studies of immunomodulatory therapy clearly indicate that these tumors are sensitive to a new class of screening inhibitors that have previously demonstrated effectiveness in the treatment of tumors with known immunogenicity, such as melanoma. Scientifically proven combinations of drugs to further stimulate immunity should be tested in the treatment of all biological subtypes of breast cancer. The isolation of components of the tumor's immune environment, which allows for a more accurate prognosis of the disease, also contributes to the consideration of methods for modifying this immune environment in order to improve the prognosis for the treatment of tumors that do not contain TIL. (1) Various molecular and biological features of breast cancer and the prevalence of the process determine the polymorphism of possible approaches to the treatment of this subtype of cancer. Unfortunately, none of the existing approaches currently provides stable results. Neoadjuvant systemic therapy is the most important stage of treatment, allowing the tumor to be transferred to an operable state. The effectiveness of the drugs used is assessed by repeated mor-

phological examination. According to the analysis of modern publications by domestic and foreign authors, it can be concluded that the use of PCTs in neoadjuvant and adjuvant regimens, with the inclusion of anthracyclines, dose-sealed taxanes and platinum preparations in the treatment regimen, allows in most cases to achieve a complete clinical and histological response, as well as to increase disease-free and overall survival of patients. These regimens are preferable compared to the standard three-week administration regimen. The priority areas in the treatment of breast cancer are the search for new chemotherapy regimens, targeted drugs, further study of the structure and function of the tumor's immune microenvironment and, as a result, the creation of new immunomodulatory drugs. (9) The absolute number of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TIL's type I lymphocytes) is important in providing the body's potential immune defense against the tumor [10,11,12]. The increase in the number of TIL's is most pronounced in breast cancer. The pathogenetic pathway through PD1/PDL1 expression plays a major role in the immune response to tumor growth. As a result of studies evaluating the presence of PD 1 on TIL and PD-L1 on breast cancer cells, it was found that immune checkpoint proteins are overexpressed in many types of breast cancer, but especially often in triple-negative cancer [13,14]. The PD 1 receptor is expressed on the surface of up to 50% of TIL, and PDL1 is present on 45% of breast cancer cells. When a T cell interacts through the PD 1 receptor with the corresponding receptor on antigen-presenting cells (APC) or a tumor cell (for example, PD-L1), this T cell is inactivated [13,14]. In 2014 The results of a phase 1 study of the anti-PD-L1 monoclonal antibody MPDL3280A in the treatment of metastatic breast cancer have been published [13]. International clinical trials are currently underway to treat patients with PD-L1 positive breast cancer using atezolizumab [13, 15, 16]. Atezolizumab is a humanized anti-PD-L1 antibody that inhibits the attachment of PD-L1 to PD 1 and B7.1, but leaves the PD-L2/Pd 1 coupling intact [14,15,16]. The studies plan to evaluate the effectiveness of the combination of atezolizumab with nab-paclitaxel in metastatic breast cancer. The recruitment of patients for research continues. Nab-paclitaxel is characterized by high antitumor activity [17].

Conclusion. Recently, it has been recognized that the tumor microenvironment is one of the main factors of tumor progression and drug resistance. Immunotherapy is a promising area of search for new ways in the treatment of patients with malignant tumors. The main purpose of immunotherapy is to regulate the immune control of tumor cells. In 2019, atezolizumab was included in the clinical recommendations of the Association of Oncologists and Radiologists. The indication for the use of nab-paclitaxel is inoperable locally advanced or metastatic breast cancer in the first line of therapy in combination with nab-paclitaxel in the presence of PD-L1 expression.

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